

CHEMISTRY

STUDY OF THE PROCESS OF PRELIMINARY AROMATIZATION OF REFORMING FEEDSTOCK ON A ZEOLITE-CONTAINING CATALYST

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Abstract

Due to the growth in automobile gasoline consumption, the reduction of global oil reserves, and the continuous introduction of new requirements for the quality of motor fuels and their chemical composition, great attention is paid to improving catalytic reforming technologies [5]. The efficiency of the reforming process as a whole can be increased through the development and implementation of new catalysts, as well as through the improvement of technological equipment and process schemes. A zeolite-containing catalyst was used as the object of the study. The further direction of research was determined — the selection of optimal operating parameters for a zeolite-containing dehydrocyclooligomerization catalyst under the conditions of the preliminary aromatization process of reforming feedstock. All processes were carried out in the temperature range of 300–400 °C, at a pressure of 1 MPa, with a volumetric feed rate from 1 h⁻¹ to 4 h⁻¹. The highest content of aromatic hydrocarbons was recorded in samples obtained at temperatures of 350 °C and 375 °C — 18.7 vol.% and 17.9 vol.% respectively, which corresponds to an increase of 7.9 wt.% and 7.1 wt.% compared to the feedstock. The difference in aromatic hydrocarbon content between samples obtained at volumetric feed rates of 1 h⁻¹ and 4 h⁻¹ is relatively small and amounts to 2.1 vol.%.

Keywords: reforming, catalyst, aromatization, arenes, process temperature.

Introduction

One of the most crucial procedures in the contemporary petrochemical and oil refining industries is catalytic reforming. Catalytic reforming has two main purposes: 1) production of aromatic hydrocarbons — benzene, toluene, and xylenes; 2) production of high-octane components of automotive gasolines.

Hydrogen-rich gas, which has a high hydrogen content and is frequently utilized in hydrogenation operations, is another important byproduct of the catalytic reforming process.

According to recent data, the total global capacity of the reforming process is about 14 million barrels per day (600 million tons per year), of which two-thirds operate in the gasoline mode for the production of high-octane gasoline components, and one-third operate in the aromatic mode for the production of individual aromatic hydrocarbons [7].

At present, 51 catalytic reforming units with a total capacity of about 30 million tons per year are operating at Russian oil refineries. Of these, 45 units with a total capacity of 27 million tons per year operate in the gasoline mode, and 6 units operate in the aromatic mode (3 million tons per year) [7].

In Russia, the development of reforming technology is carried out in three main directions.

- optimization of technological operating conditions in order to increase process severity and the yield of target products;
- modernization of existing catalysts and development of completely new catalysts;
- improvement of technological flow schemes in order to increase the octane number without reducing the yield of target products, as well as reducing the content of aromatic hydrocarbons in reformat [1].

The majority of catalytic reforming units in Russia were built during the Soviet period. Due to the long service life of these units, reconstruction and modernization require significant capital investments. Therefore, at present, a more economically feasible option is the development and implementation of new catalysts.

Bifunctional catalysts are used in the catalytic reforming process. At the initial stage of industrial development of catalytic reforming, oxide catalysts or alumina–molybdenum catalysts were mainly used. Later, platinum catalysts were introduced, which gave a strong impetus to the development of the catalytic reforming process.

The high cost of platinum predetermined its low content in the catalyst and led to the subsequent creation of platinum–rhenium catalysts. In such catalysts, the platinum content ranges from 0.3 to 0.7 wt.% [2; 6].

Over time, a decrease in catalyst activity occurs. This is associated with coke deposition on the catalyst surface, as well as with a reduction in platinum dispersion, since the accumulation of poisons takes place, which cannot be removed.

To restore activity, a regeneration process is applied; however, even after regeneration, the catalyst does not fully recover its initial activity, which ultimately leads to the need for catalyst replacement over time.

A specific feature of considering the use of zeolite-containing catalysts is that their application in the catalytic reforming process makes it possible to reduce the process temperature. Process temperature affects catalyst activity, which in turn determines the duration of the regeneration cycle.

A short regeneration cycle is characterized by frequent process shutdowns and, consequently, interruption of product output, as well as increased costs for catalyst regeneration [4].

A catalytic system using a zeolite-containing catalyst for low-temperature reforming is presented in [9]. The authors developed a catalytic system consisting of three reactors connected in series. The first reactor contains a catalyst with an AEL-structure zeolite, while the second and third reactors contain a catalyst with an LTL-structure zeolite.

Results Obtained

The advantages of using zeolite-containing catalysts lie in their low cost and the possibility of their application in processes for producing motor fuels from wide fractions of hydrocarbon feedstock without preliminary treatment.

It is known that, in addition to the dehydrogenation of cycloalkanes, the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons in the reforming process occurs as a result of alkane dehydrocyclization [102]. However, in the tail reactors, linear and iso-alkanes enter hydrocracking reactions at a significant rate, which contribute to an increase in the octane number of reformat due to the concentration of arenes, while simultaneously reducing

the overall reformat yield. The involvement of C7–C10 alkanes in aromatic formation reactions makes it possible to optimally utilize the feedstock potential and increase the overall efficiency of the process.

A catalyst containing zeolite was selected as the subject of the investigation. The experiments were performed at temperatures between 300 and 400 °C, under a pressure of 1 MPa, with a volumetric feed rate of 1 h⁻¹.

It was established that the use of a zeolite-containing catalyst in the gasoline aromatization process promotes the formation of arenes from alkanes, without significantly affecting hydrocarbons of cyclic structure — the maximum reduction in cycloalkane content is 4.6 wt.%.

The change in aromatic hydrocarbon content with increasing temperature in the feedstock and gasoline aromatization products on a zeolite catalyst is shown in Figure 1.

The highest content of aromatic hydrocarbons was recorded in samples obtained at temperatures of 350 °C and 375 °C — 18.7 vol.% and 17.9 vol.% respectively, which corresponds to an increase of 7.9 wt.% and 7.1 wt.% compared to the feedstock.

Figure 1. Change in the content of aromatic hydrocarbons with increasing temperature in the feedstock and gasoline aromatization products on a zeolite-containing catalyst

Figure 2 shows the hydrocarbon composition of the feedstock and gasoline aromatization products on a zeolite-containing catalyst.

- alkanes,
- isoalkanes,
- cycloalkanes,
- arenes,
- alkenes.

Figure 2. Hydrocarbon composition of the feedstock and gasoline aromatization products on a zeolite-containing catalyst

The assumption of selectivity of the zeolite-containing catalyst toward linear alkanes is confirmed by a decrease in their content by 12.3 wt.% and 11.0 wt.%.

Figure 3. Change in the yield of gasoline aromatization products on catalyst 4 with increasing temperature

A decrease in the catalyst yield when the process temperature is increased to 400 °C, along with a relative reduction in the share of arenes in liquid products compared to catalysts obtained at lower temperatures, is presumably a consequence of intensified hydrocracking reactions. The yield of liquid products decreases from 97.8 wt.% to 90.1 wt.% when the temperature reaches 350 °C, and with further temperature increase changes insignificantly.

Further, to evaluate the influence of the listed factors on the efficiency of using a zeolite-containing catalyst in the gasoline aromatization process, experiments were carried out in which the volumetric feed rate was maintained from 1 h⁻¹ to 4 h⁻¹. The initial process temperature was 300 °C and was increased, at intervals of 25 °C, up to 400 °C (Figures 4–6) [8].

Figure 4. Dependence of arene content in gasoline aromatization products on a zeolite-containing catalyst on the volumetric feed rate ($t = 300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

It was established that at a temperature of $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, in the presence of hydrogen-containing gas, the content of aromatic hydrocarbons decreases with an increase in volumetric feed rate from 11.8 vol.% to 10.8 vol.%. The increase in arene content compared to the feedstock under these experimental conditions is insignificant — from 1.1 wt.% to 1.7 wt.%, depending on the volumetric feed rate.

Figure 5. Dependence of aromatic hydrocarbon content in gasoline aromatization products on catalyst 4 on the volumetric feed rate ($t = 350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

It was determined that the arene content in process products decreases with increasing volumetric feed rate from 1 h^{-1} to 4 h^{-1} from 13.2 vol.% to 11.3 vol.%.

Within the framework of the experiment, the highest amount of aromatic hydrocarbons was recorded in process products obtained at a temperature of $400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The process products obtained in the volumetric feed rate range from 1 h^{-1} to 4 h^{-1} contain from 14.1 vol.% to 16.2 vol.% of aromatic hydrocarbons. At the same time, the maximum increase in arene content compared to the feedstock is 5.4 wt.%.

Figure 6. Dependence of aromatic hydrocarbon content in gasoline aromatization products on catalyst 4 on the volumetric feed rate ($t = 400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

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